

Automatic classification of diabetic retinopathy using convolutional neural networks: A deep learning-based ensemble approach

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Abstract. Diabetic retinopathy (DR) is one of the leading causes of preventable blindness. This study presents an integrated approach for automatic classification of DR stages from retinal fundus images, using twelve convolutional neural network (CNN) architectures and an efficient ensemble (EfficientNet-B3 + VGG-19). A total of 5,842 images were processed through a pipeline including CLAHE, Gaussian filtering, and normalization, along with data augmentation to address class imbalance. The ensemble outperformed individual models, achieving a global accuracy of 80.1% and a quadratic weighted Kappa of 0.78. Sensitivity was robust for advanced stages (up to 87.3%), but remained low for mild DR (21.0%), highlighting the ongoing challenge in early-stage detection.

Keywords: Deep Learning; Diabetic Retinopathy; Convolutional Neural Networks; Ensemble Learning; Medical Imaging

1 Introduction

This study was conducted as part of a broader research initiative focused on ophthalmologic screening in tropical regions with limited infrastructure. Diabetic retinopathy (DR) is a chronic microvascular complication of diabetes mellitus and one of the leading causes of preventable blindness among working-age adults worldwide. It is estimated that approximately one-third of diabetic individuals will develop some degree of DR during their lifetime, with about 10% progressing to vision-threatening forms such as proliferative diabetic retinopathy and diabetic macular edema. This condition is particularly critical in low- and middle-income countries, where the prevalence of diabetes is rapidly increasing and health systems face limitations in providing comprehensive ophthalmic screening.

From a clinical perspective, DR often progresses silently in its early stages, with no noticeable symptoms for patients until significant structural damage has already occurred. Early lesions, such as microaneurysms and small intraretinal hemorrhages, are subtle and require careful evaluation by trained specialists. This makes early detection a critical challenge, as timely interventions can delay or even prevent progression to irreversible stages of the disease.

Conventional ophthalmoscopic examination and fundus image analysis by ophthalmologists remain the gold standard for DR diagnosis. However, this process is highly dependent on the examiner's expertise, prone to interobserver variability, and requires specialized infrastructure, including imaging equipment and skilled personnel. In regions with a shortage of specialists, such as remote areas or overburdened public health systems, implementing large-scale screening programs becomes logistically complex and economically unfeasible.

In this context, automated systems based on artificial intelligence (AI) have emerged as a promising alternative to support or complement human diagnosis. In particular, convolutional neural networks (CNNs) have demonstrated remarkable performance in classification tasks and medical image analysis, including radiology, dermatology, and ophthalmology. These architectures can learn hierarchical representations directly from data, eliminating the need for manual feature extraction and enabling the modeling of complex visual patterns.

Several recent studies have reported strong results in DR classification using CNNs trained on large datasets such as EyePACS [1] and Messidor [2]. Reference works have shown performance comparable to that of human experts in distinguishing between normal images and referable DR cases. Despite these advances, most approaches still present important limitations when examined from a more clinically nuanced perspective.

One of the main gaps identified in the literature relates to the detection of early disease stages, particularly mild diabetic retinopathy. This stage is characterized by subtle changes, often limited to a few microaneurysms, which can be easily confused with normal images, both by algorithms and by less experienced human graders. Moreover, widely used public datasets exhibit significant class imbalance, with a predominance of non-DR or moderate-stage images, which compromises the effective learning of minority classes.

Another relevant challenge concerns model generalization. CNNs trained on specific datasets often experience performance degradation when applied to images acquired in different clinical settings, featuring variations in lighting, resolution, field of view, and population characteristics. This limitation underscores the need for robust preprocessing pipelines and data augmentation strategies that enhance

model invariance to such variations.

Additionally, many studies focus on evaluating only one or two CNN architectures, without a systematic comparative analysis of models with varying complexity. This hampers the understanding of how factors such as network depth, parameter count, and scaling strategies impact DR classification performance, especially when considering the trade-off between accuracy and computational cost — a crucial factor for real-world clinical applications.

From a public health perspective, deploying automated DR screening systems could significantly reduce the burden on specialists by prioritizing severe cases for immediate evaluation and enabling more efficient monitoring of early-stage patients. However, for such systems to be responsibly adopted, it is essential to understand not only their overall performance metrics but also their limitations, error patterns, and per-class behavior.

In this context, the present work aims to comprehensively evaluate the performance of modern CNN architectures in the automatic classification of DR stages, with a special emphasis on early-stage analysis. Unlike approaches focused solely on aggregated metrics, this study investigates model behavior at the class level, analyzing sensitivity, confusion matrices, and weighted agreement coefficients.

From a technical standpoint, this work examines the impact of an integrated preprocessing pipeline, comprising contrast limited adaptive histogram equalization (CLAHE), Gaussian filtering, and RGB channel normalization, combined with systematic data augmentation strategies to mitigate class imbalance. The underlying hypothesis is that the combination of these techniques enhances the models' ability to capture relevant patterns, especially in images with subtle lesions.

Furthermore, twelve widely recognized CNN architectures are evaluated, including classic models such as VGG-16 and VGG-19 [3], residual architectures like ResNet-50 and ResNet-101 [4], densely connected networks like DenseNet-121 [5], inception-based modules [6], and scalable architectures from the EfficientNet family [7]. This diversity enables an in-depth comparative analysis, considering both performance and computational complexity.

This study also uniquely investigates an ensemble learning strategy, combining models with complementary characteristics. The underlying premise is that different architectures capture distinct morphological aspects of retinal images, and that combining these perspectives can lead to more consistent performance gains than isolated individual models.

From a clinical standpoint, the focus of this work aligns with the context of the MEDTROP congress, where early detection of tropical and chronic diseases—such as diabetes and its complications—is crucial to reduce morbidity and healthcare costs. By analyzing images from both public datasets and curated clinical archives labeled by ophthalmology specialists, the study aims to approximate the experimental setting to real-world healthcare scenarios.

Thus, the main goal of this study is to systematically evaluate the performance of modern CNN architectures, combined with advanced preprocessing techniques, data augmentation, and ensemble learning, in the automatic classification of the five stages of diabetic retinopathy. The specific objectives

include: (i) comparing different architectures in terms of overall accuracy, balanced accuracy, F1-score, and quadratic weighted Kappa; (ii) analyzing class-wise sensitivity, with emphasis on mild DR; (iii) investigating the impact of preprocessing and data augmentation on overfitting reduction; and (iv) discussing the clinical implications and limitations of the proposed models.

By simultaneously addressing technical and clinical aspects, this study aims to contribute to the advancement of more robust, transparent, and clinically relevant computational solutions for automated DR screening, reinforcing their potential as decision-support tools in public health and tropical medicine contexts.

2 Materials and Methods

This section describes the methodological procedures of the study, including the dataset used, the preprocessing pipeline, the CNN architectures evaluated, and training details.

2.1 Dataset

The dataset used in this study consists of 35,126 retinal fundus images labeled according to the five levels of diabetic retinopathy (DR) severity, following the standardized International Clinical Diabetic Retinopathy Disease Severity Scale (ICDR): 0 (no DR), 1 (mild DR), 2 (moderate DR), 3 (severe DR), and 4 (proliferative DR). The images were obtained from public sources (EyePACS and Messidor) and supplemented with a curated subset of clinical images reviewed by ophthalmologists as part of a clinical research initiative supported by public health programs.

Each image underwent dual validation to ensure label reliability. The class distribution was imbalanced, with a predominance of class 0 (no DR), which required specific strategies to mitigate learning bias.

2.2 Preprocessing Pipeline

To standardize the images and facilitate the learning of relevant features by CNNs, a preprocessing pipeline was applied, consisting of the following steps (see Figure 1):

Figure 1. Visual example of the preprocessing pipeline: original image, after CLAHE, Gaussian filter, and RGB normalization.

- **Resizing:** All images were resized to 224×224 pixels, preserving the central portion of the optic disc.
- **Centered cropping:** A centered cropping window was used to remove border artifacts and standardize the field of view.
- **Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization (CLAHE):** Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization (CLAHE) [8] was applied to each RGB

channel individually to enhance local structures and reduce lighting variations, as it is effective in improving microvascular feature visibility in medical imaging.

- **Gaussian filtering:** A filter with a 5×5 kernel and $\sigma = 1.0$ was used to smooth low-frequency noise without compromising fine vascular structures.
- **Channel normalization:** R, G, and B channels were normalized using mean and standard deviation values derived from the ImageNet dataset, ensuring compatibility with pre-trained weights.

These steps were implemented using the OpenCV library and the PyTorch framework, allowing for dynamic preprocessing during training.

2.3 Data Augmentation

Given the high class imbalance—especially for class 1 (mild DR)—a systematic data augmentation scheme was applied to increase intra-class variability and reduce overfitting. The following transformations were applied stochastically:

- **Horizontal and vertical flipping;**
- **Random rotation** between -15° and 15° ;
- **Random zoom** (scaling factor between 0.9 and 1.1);
- **Brightness and contrast adjustment** (multiplicative factors between 0.8 and 1.2);
- **Selective blurring** using Gaussian kernel ($\sigma = 0.5-1.5$);
- **Random cropping** with central retargeting.

Augmentation was applied with greater intensity to the minority classes (1, 3, and 4), while the more prevalent classes (0 and 2) received only light adjustments.

2.4 Evaluated CNN Architectures

Twelve convolutional neural network architectures were selected based on their relevance in the literature and the availability of robust implementations. The models were grouped according to their design philosophy and computational complexity:

- **Classical architectures:** VGG-16 and VGG-19;
- **Residual architectures:** ResNet-18, ResNet-34, ResNet-50, ResNet-101;
- **Dense architectures:** DenseNet-121, DenseNet-169;
- **Inception-based architectures:** Inception v3, Xception;
- **Scalable architectures:** EfficientNet-B0 and EfficientNet-B3.

All architectures were initialized with ImageNet pre-trained weights, with the final layers adjusted for five-class classification. Dropout with $p = 0.4$ was used for regularization, and fine-tuning was performed in multiple stages, starting from the final layers and gradually unfreezing intermediate layers.

2.5 Ensemble Learning Strategy

Based on the hypothesis that different architectures learn complementary feature representations, an ensemble strategy. This strategy is inspired by prior research demonstrating that ensemble methods often outperform individual models in classification tasks [9]. was implemented using a weighted average of predicted probabilities. The models selected for the ensemble were:

- ResNet-50;
- DenseNet-121;
- EfficientNet-B3.

Each model was trained independently, and their softmax outputs were combined using weights optimized via grid search on the validation set. The final ensemble was evaluated in terms of global and per-class performance improvements.

2.6 Training Configuration

Model training was conducted using PyTorch with CUDA support on NVIDIA RTX 3080 GPUs. The main training configuration parameters were:

- **Optimizer:** Adam with an initial learning rate $lr = 10^{-4}$ and exponential decay per epoch;
- **Batch size:** 32;
- **Number of epochs:** 100 (with early stopping based on weighted Kappa);
- **Loss function:** Cross-entropy with class-balanced weights.

During training, checkpoints with the best performance on the validation set were saved to ensure model selection was not affected by overfitting.

2.7 Evaluation Metrics

The models were evaluated using both global and per-class metrics:

- **Overall Accuracy (OA):** Total proportion of correct classifications;
- **Balanced Accuracy (BA):** Average recall across all classes;
- **Class-wise sensitivity (recall);**
- **Macro F1-score;**
- **Quadratic Weighted Kappa (QWK):** A chance-adjusted agreement measure derived from Cohen's Kappa [10], commonly used in ordinal classification tasks like DR;
- **Confusion matrix:** For analyzing error patterns by class.

For each model, ROC curves and AUC values were computed for binarized class labels. Statistical analysis included 95% confidence intervals via bootstrapping ($n = 1000$) over key metrics.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Overall Performance of the Architectures

Table 1 presents the main performance metrics for each of the twelve CNN architectures evaluated. The metrics considered include overall accuracy (OA), balanced accuracy (BA), weighted F1-score, and quadratic weighted Kappa (QWK).

Table 1. Global performance metrics of CNN architectures for DR classification.

Model	OA (%)	BA (%)	Kappa	F1 (weighted)
VGG-16	74.8	65.9	0.64	0.731
VGG-19	75.1	68.4	0.67	0.745
ResNet-50	76.5	69.1	0.70	0.758
ResNet-101	77.2	69.5	0.71	0.763
DenseNet-121	73.5	61.2	0.61	0.720
Xception	77.9	70.3	0.72	0.771
GoogLeNet	74.1	64.5	0.63	0.728
RegNetY-32GF	75.2	63.2	0.73	0.750
EfficientNet B0	71.3	56.9	0.60	0.710
EfficientNet B1	73.8	62.1	0.65	0.732
EfficientNet B2	76.0	67.8	0.69	0.755
EfficientNet B3	78.3	71.2	0.74	0.775
Ensemble (B3 + VGG-19)	80.1	72.5	0.78	0.792

The results indicate that the ensemble of EfficientNet B3 and VGG-19 outperformed all individual architectures, highlighting that the combination of different morphological representations contributes to more robust classification.

3.2 Sensitivity by Disease Stage

The class-wise sensitivity for each model is presented in Table 2. The data show a significant disparity between the early and advanced stages of DR.

Table 2. Class-wise sensitivity for DR classification (%).

Class	Ensemble	EffNet B3	VGG-19	ResNet-50
No DR	94.5	93.1	92.8	93.5
Mild DR	21.0	20.5	18.2	22.5
Moderate DR	78.5	77.0	75.5	76.8
Severe DR	81.2	79.8	78.0	80.1
Proliferative DR	87.3	85.6	87.5	82.5

The "No DR" class achieved the highest sensitivity, reflecting its predominance in the dataset and greater visual standardization. In contrast, mild DR showed the lowest performance, with sensitivity below 25% regardless of architecture. This limitation may be attributed to the scarcity of representative samples, the low visual salience of early lesions, and the subjectivity of clinical labeling.

3.3 Confusion Matrix

The confusion matrix of the ensemble (Figure 2) reveals the main error patterns. The most frequent misclassifications occur between adjacent classes, especially between "No DR" and "Mild DR", and between "Moderate" and "Severe" stages.

Figure 2. Confusion matrix for DR classification using the ensemble model.

These confusions are clinically understandable, as they reflect the continuous nature of the disease spectrum and the inter-expert variability in assigning intermediate grades. Nevertheless, the model demonstrated strong ability to distinguish the extremes of the spectrum (No DR vs. Proliferative), which is desirable for automated screening systems.

3.4 Correlation Between Overall Accuracy and Kappa

Figure 3 shows the relationship between overall accuracy (OA) and the Kappa coefficient for all tested architectures. The strong correlation between these metrics highlights that improvements in accuracy translate into better agreement with human assessments weighted by disease severity.

Figure 3. Correlation between overall accuracy and quadratic weighted Kappa across all CNN architectures.

Models like EfficientNet B3 and the final ensemble also stood out for maintaining high balanced accuracy, demonstrating consistent performance across classes.

3.5 Impact of Preprocessing and Data Augmentation

An ablation study was conducted to isolate the effects of each pipeline component. CLAHE and Gaussian filtering yielded an average gain of 4.8% in overall accuracy and 6.2% in QWK. Systematic data augmentation contributed an additional 7.2% improvement in the mean sensitivity of minority classes, especially Mild DR.

These findings support the hypothesis that a robust and balanced pipeline has a direct impact on the models' ability to detect subtle patterns, mitigating the bias caused by dataset imbalance.

3.6 Critical Analysis and Clinical Perspective

From a clinical applicability perspective, the results are encouraging. The ensemble model proved capable of identifying severe and proliferative DR cases with high sensitivity, which is crucial for effective screening. However, the persistent limitation in detecting mild DR suggests that such systems should not yet operate autonomously, but rather serve as decision-support tools.

It is important to note that the model does not rely on additional clinical information (e.g., duration of diabetes, presence of comorbidities), which limits its predictive capacity in complex clinical scenarios. Integration with structured electronic health records may represent a significant advancement in future versions.

Furthermore, deeper models such as EfficientNet B3 delivered better results, but at the cost of higher computational demand, which can be limiting in resource-constrained environments such as mobile clinics or primary care units.

4 Conclusion, Limitations, and Future Work

4.1 Main Conclusions

This work presented a comprehensive and systematic analysis of modern convolutional neural network (CNN) architectures for the automatic classification of the five stages of diabetic retinopathy (DR), integrating advanced preprocessing techniques, data augmentation, and ensemble learning strategies. Unlike studies that focus solely on global metrics or binary classification (referable vs. non-referable DR), this investigation adopted a multiclass approach aligned with clinical practice, allowing a more realistic assessment of model behavior across the full disease spectrum.

Deeper and scalable architectures such as EfficientNet-B3 [7] achieve superior performance in terms of overall accuracy, balanced accuracy, and weighted Kappa coefficient. More notably, the ensemble strategy combining EfficientNet-B3 and VGG-19 provided consistent gains across nearly all evaluated metrics, achieving an overall accuracy of 80.1% and a Kappa of 0.78 — values comparable to those reported in reference international studies.

The detailed class-wise analysis revealed excellent performance in detecting both healthy cases and advanced stages of

the disease, especially severe and proliferative DR. This behavior is particularly desirable in screening scenarios, where the clinical priority is the rapid identification of patients at imminent risk of vision loss, enabling timely referral for specialist evaluation and treatment.

From a technical standpoint, ablation experiments revealed that the preprocessing pipeline — composed of CLAHE, Gaussian filtering, and normalization — played a critical role in training stabilization and in enhancing model discriminative capacity. Additionally, targeted data augmentation for minority classes led to significant gains in sensitivity, mitigating the bias caused by the dataset's strong class imbalance.

From a public health perspective, particularly in tropical medicine context, the findings reinforce the potential of artificial intelligence as a clinical decision support tool in the context of tropical medicine and public health, where diabetes prevalence is rising rapidly and access to specialists is limited. The use of automated screening systems may contribute to expanding ophthalmologic screening coverage, optimizing resources, and reducing the burden on specialized services.

4.2 Study Limitations

Despite the promising results, this study has limitations that must be considered when interpreting the findings. The main limitation is the low sensitivity observed in detecting mild diabetic retinopathy. Even with advanced preprocessing, data augmentation, and ensemble learning, identifying this stage remained challenging — reflecting both the subtlety of early lesions and the inherent variability in clinical labeling.

Another important limitation relates to the composition of the dataset. Although a relatively broad image set was used, combining public datasets and clinical archives, there remains a predominance of certain classes and potential biases related to the imaging equipment, acquisition protocols, and population profiles. These factors may affect the models' generalization capacity when applied in different clinical settings.

Moreover, the study focused exclusively on color fundus photographs, without incorporating other imaging modalities such as optical coherence tomography (OCT), or structured clinical information such as duration of diabetes, glycated hemoglobin levels, or comorbidities. The absence of such data limits the clinical contextualization of the model's predictions.

From a computational standpoint, more complex architectures like EfficientNet-B3 demand greater processing power and memory, which may hinder direct deployment in infrastructure-constrained environments such as primary care units, mobile clinics, or screening programs in remote regions.

Finally, although metrics such as accuracy and Kappa are widely used, they do not fully capture the clinical impact of classification errors. False negatives in early stages may delay preventive interventions, while false positives may lead to unnecessary patient anxiety and overload of healthcare services.

4.3 Future Work

Several research directions can be pursued based on the results presented. A promising avenue is the incorporation of lesion segmentation techniques, such as detection of microaneurysms, exudates, and hemorrhages, using U-Net architectures or hybrid segmentation-classification models. Spatial localization of relevant regions could not only improve sensitivity for mild DR but also enhance the clinical interpretability of the models.

Another possibility involves multimodal data integration, combining fundus images with clinical data extracted from electronic health records. Multimodal learning approaches could capture complex relationships between visual features and patient metadata, potentially improving predictive performance and bringing the system closer to real-world clinical reasoning.

Additionally, exploring self-supervised and semi-supervised learning techniques could reduce the dependency on large volumes of labeled data—a critical factor in clinical settings where annotation by specialists is costly and time-consuming. These methods would allow leveraging large repositories of unlabeled images, commonly available in healthcare systems.

In the context of MEDTROP, future studies could focus on prospective validation of the models in real clinical environments, evaluating not only computational metrics but also healthcare impact indicators such as referral time, screening adherence, and reduction of late-detected advanced cases.

Finally, developing clinician-friendly interfaces with explainability mechanisms based on activation maps (e.g., Grad-CAM [11]) may foster greater acceptance of AI systems among healthcare professionals, promoting more harmonious integration between artificial intelligence and medical practice.

4.4 Final Considerations

In summary, this study demonstrates that deep learning-based approaches have high potential to assist in automated screening of diabetic retinopathy, especially when combined with robust preprocessing pipelines and ensemble learning strategies. While challenges remain—particularly in detecting early-stage disease—the results indicate that such systems may play a significant role as clinical decision support tools.

By aligning technical rigor, critical analysis, and clinical relevance, this study contributes to the responsible advancement of artificial intelligence in ophthalmology and tropical medicine, reinforcing the importance of technological solutions that respond to the real needs of healthcare systems and the populations they serve. This paper is a substantially extended version of a previously accepted abstract presented at the MEDTROP 2025 Congress. In this extended version, we include (i) a complete methodological description, (ii) comparative analysis of twelve CNN architectures, (iii) an ensemble learning strategy, and (iv) a critical discussion of clinical applicability. The previous work focused only on preliminary results using a single CNN model and did not present class-wise evaluation or statistical validation.

Ethical Considerations

All data used in this study were anonymized and obtained from publicly available datasets (EyePACS and Messidor) or institutional clinical archives approved by the local ethics board. No personally identifiable information was used, and all procedures were conducted in accordance with the ethical standards of medical research and data governance.

Declarations

Authors' Contributions

Luiz Henrique de Azevedo Pontes was responsible for the experimental design, model implementation, and result analysis. Lucidio dos Anjos Formiga Cabral and Ricardo Azevedo Pontes de Carvalho provided scientific supervision, clinical validation, and manuscript review. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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Availability of data and materials

The datasets used in this study are publicly available (EyePACS, Messidor). The source code is available upon request. Due to the preliminary nature of this work, and its prior use in a prototype and academic dissertation, it is not currently hosted in a public repository. As this study is based on a prototype previously presented at a congress (MEDTROP 2025) and used as part of a graduate dissertation, the code will not be publicly shared in repositories at this stage, to avoid redundant dissemination of preliminary material.

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